

LASER TRANSMISSION WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC POLYURETHANES: A ROBUST PROCESS WITH HIGH RELIABILITY

R. Staehr¹, V. Wippo¹, P. Jaeschke¹, O. Suttmann¹, L. Overmeyer¹

¹Laser Zentrum Hannover e.V., Hollerithallee 8, 30419 Hannover, Germany

Email: r.staehr@lzh.de, v.wippo@lzh.de, p.jaeschke@lzh.de, o.suttmann@lzh.de, l.overmeyer@lzh.de

Web page: <http://www.lzh.de>

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the laser transmission welding process as an advantageous joining technique and investigates its characteristics for welding thermoplastic polyurethanes (TPU). Laser power, feed rate, and clamping pressure are all variable parameters that influence the weld seam quality, and have been described and analyzed in detail in this paper. This process has been shown to be characterized by a wide processing parameter field and exhibits excellent monitoring and automation capability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic Polyurethanes (TPU) bridge the gap between rubber and solid thermoplastic materials, combining the meltability of thermoplastics with the elastic properties of rubbers. In addition, the recyclability, chemical resistance and wear resistance of TPUs have made them a widely used material in the construction, automotive, electronics, medical, sports and leisure industries. Due to expanding industrial applications the demand of TPU has continuously increased in recent years and is expected to further follow this trend in the years to come [1]. Typical efficient and high volume production methods, such as injection molding, are able to cover an extensive range of geometries, but once the production method becomes inadequate for the part for reasons such as complexity or scalability, the production step must then also include a joining process. If such a joining step is needed, a key determinant for the efficiency and reliability of production, is how optimized the joining technique is. Although the welding of TPU materials is mentioned in various sources, they mostly refer to joining techniques such as fusion bonding, hot knife, hot plate, ultrasonic, high frequency, heat impulse or friction welding [2]. The few sources that mention laser welding are mostly applied for foils or films and do not go into detail with regards to the description of the welding process or results [3]. In comparison to the other joining techniques of thermoplastics, laser transmission welding offers the specific benefits of being a highly flexible process, working in absence of tool wear and vibrational loading, having a well-defined and localized heat input, and its suitability to integrate monitoring and control options [4].

The working principle of laser transmission welding relies on the optical transparency of the thermoplastic material in the range of near infrared radiation (see Figure 1). The joining of two overlapping components involves the laser radiation passing through a natural, non-absorbing thermoplastic (laser transparent part, LT) until it can be absorbed by the adjoined part, usually containing carbon black or another absorbing additive. The heat generated by the absorbed radiation is conducted to the overlapped interface, locally melting both parts and in the process producing the weld seam. In order to ensure homogeneous heat conduction in the interface between the parts, a uniform clamping pressure has to be applied along the whole weld seam [5]. Among various strategies that exist for laser transmission welding, contour and quasi-simultaneous welding are often used. In contour welding, the weld seam is generated by a single pass of the laser beam on a defined contour. This technique is preferably used to generate long weld seams. Quasi-simultaneous welding describes a strategy in which the laser beam is deflected by moving mirrors in a scanner optic. The beam is redirected and scanned rapidly over the entire joining region at once, allowing the process energy

input and heat generation to develop slowly. In order to apply sufficient energy for the joining process, during quasi-simultaneous welding the laser beam passes the contour several times (multiple passes).

Figure 1: Laser transmission welding principle.

In order to better establish laser based welding of TPU materials in industry, the published content detailing processing characteristics, setup and results needs to be made more comprehensive and explicit. This present work gives an overview of the subjects mentioned and demonstrates the capabilities of this process.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The TPU material used in the experiments was an Elastollan[®] 1185A compound produced by BASF. Since laser transmission welding processes require both a laser transparent (LT) material and laser absorbing (LA) partner, the material featured in these experiments consisted of a natural (transparent) TPU component coupled with a carbon black (c.b.) masterbatch (absorbing) mate (see Table 1).

Table 1: TPU material used for the experimental work.

Material	Additive	Thickness (mm)	LTW type
BASF Elastollan [®] 1185A	- (natural)	1.9	Laser transparent (LT)
BASF Elastollan [®] 1185A	Carbon black (c.b.)	1.9	Laser absorbing (LA)

All investigations were performed with a diode laser emitting at a wavelength of $\lambda = 940\text{nm}$ with a maximum power of $P_L = 300\text{W}$. The laser beam was guided by an optical fiber to a homogenizing optic, generating a rectangular focal point geometry between $A = 10 \times 10 \dots 10 \times 20\text{mm}^2$. The specifications are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Laser machine and focussing optics parameter.

Parameter	Value
Maximum laser power P_L (W)	300
Laser wavelength λ (nm)	940
Focal geometry homogenizing optics A (mm^2)	10x10 to 10x20

Following preliminary trials, the use of standard optics which provide a circular spot geometry, were forgone for the use of homogenizing optics to obtain a homogeneous energy distribution and thus homogenized temperature distribution within the weld seam. By doing so, it allows for the generation of a wider weld seam, with enhanced gap bridging capabilities. A qualitative comparison between the weld seam generated from standard optics with that of the homogenized optics is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Weld seam geometry for different optics and focal plane settings.

In addition to the laser source and homogenizing optics, the experimental setup also featured an exhaust used to remove process potential emissions. Adequate clamping pressure for proper heat transfer between mated parts was achieved through the use of a pneumatic clamping against a transparent glass plate. As a result, the beam also had to pass through the glass plate before reaching the test parts. A linear stage system was used to regulate and control the feed rate and so welding speed. The setup is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Experimental setup with homogenizer optics.

For the experiments the laser power was set to $P_L = [100 / 200]W$. For these power levels, the feed rate was varied in the range of $v = 500 \dots 10000 \text{ mm/min}$ to determine the best resulting weld strength as well as the limitations of the welding process. In order to identify the effect of the clamping pressure the pressure level was set to $p = [1 / 2 / 3] \text{ bar}$. The focal geometry of the homogenizer optic was kept constant at $A = 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$. The parameters are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Experimental parameters.

Parameter	Value
Laser power P_L (W)	100 / 200
Feed rate / welding speed v (mm/min)	500...10000
Focal geometry homogenizer A (mm ²)	10x10
Clamping pressure p (bar)	1 / 2 / 3

The temperatures were detected by a high speed pyrometer HI18 by Sensortherm GmbH (see specifications in Table 4) providing a measurement frequency fast enough for a continuous and reliable temperature detection even at high welding speeds.

Table 4. Specifications of the Sensortherm HI18 pyrometer.

Sensortherm HI18	
Spectral range (μm)	1.65...2.1
Measuring range ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	120...520
Measurement spot diameter (mm)	~ 2
Measurement accuracy	$\pm 1\%$ of mean value; min. 1°C
Maximum measurement frequency (kHz)	50

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

One of the preliminary steps necessary in a laser transmission welding process is the evaluation and measurement of the spectral transmission for the source material. This gives insight into the materials compatibility with the lasers wavelength with regard to laser radiation absorption and transmission. The results for the natural TPU and the c.b. TPU are given in Figure 4, showing a very high transmission of 90% for the natural, laser transparent TPU and no transmission for the c.b. TPU. This combination can be described as ideal for transmission welding processes. However, it was already shown in [6] that even materials with low transmissivities down to $\sim 20\%$ can be welded by adapted parameters.

Figure 4: Optical transmission measurement.

Figure 5: Bead-on-plate weld results with corresponding laser power and temperature measurements.

In a next step, bead-on-plate welding without the transparent partner was performed for varying laser power at a constant feed rate of $v = 3500\text{mm/min}$ in order to evaluate the bead appearance and to determine ideal temperature ranges. The surface temperatures were synchronously measured with a pyrometer. The images shown in Figure 5 are captioned, identifying the various regions visually indicative of weld quality. Good results with molten material areas in the range of the spot geometry were obtained for temperature levels between $T = 175\dots260^\circ\text{C}$ (corresponding laser power $P_L = 40\dots60\text{W}$). The manufacturer's material specifications state that the TPU will likely begin to degrade at $T \sim 230^\circ\text{C}$; but since the degradation process is a time dependent process and the duration during welding for which the material will be at such elevated temperatures is short, the degrading effect to the mechanical properties of the material are likely to be minimal. Above this temperature, at $T \sim 280^\circ\text{C}$, the material starts to undergo visual degradation, with colour changes at the surface becoming apparent. Beginning at $T > 300^\circ\text{C}$, it can be seen that the degraded region extends to cover the entirety of the welded region. At temperatures below $T = 175^\circ\text{C}$, the weld seam width starts to decrease, beginning at the outer borders of the spot geometry, until the material is not molten even in the center area of the spot ($T < 120^\circ\text{C}$). The temperature range found gives a reference for later monitoring and control solutions, although as the following laser welding and temperature measurements were performed through both the transparent TPU material as well as the glass plate used in the clamping system, thermal radiation damping must be considered. In addition, the laser power needs to be adjusted accordingly to account for both the partial radiation absorption of the glass plate in the clamping configuration, as well as for the heat transfer at the interface between the welding partners. Therefore, in a next step different parameters were varied in order to generate strong weld seams. Test specimens were produced to evaluate the toughness of the welded specimens.

For evaluation purposes a non-standard test method was used. The specimen dimensions were kept constant at $75 \times 20\text{mm}^2$, overlapping on their full geometry. As shown in Figure 6, a weld seam was applied on both ends of the specimen. This closed geometry was clamped by two fixing bolts in clamping jaws. By applying a tensile force, the weld seam is exposed to a stress similar to a peel test on both welded ends synchronously. The maximum force recorded was divided by the weld seam (specimen) width. The measurements were performed with 5 specimens and an average value and standard deviation was calculated for the evaluation.

Figure 6: Tensile testing specimen and setup.

Figure 7: Maximum force obtained for varying laser power and feed rate at a constant spot size of $A = 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ and clamping pressure of $p = 3 \text{ bar}$.

Tensile test results were obtained from trials performed with a laser power of both $P_L = 100 \text{ W}$ and $P_L = 200 \text{ W}$ over a range of feed rates, keeping both the spot size and clamping pressure constant at $A = 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ and $p = 3 \text{ bar}$ respectively, as shown in Figure 7. For both laser power levels, a feed rate range with maximum strength values can be observed. At a laser power of $P_L = 100 \text{ W}$ and within the feed rate range of $v = 1000 \dots 4500 \text{ mm/min}$, comparable results for the weld seam strength were obtained, varying less than 9% between the highest and lowest mean strength value and having overlapping error bars. Operating the laser power at $P_L = 200 \text{ W}$, the feed rate was varied between $v = 6000 \dots 10000 \text{ mm/min}$ leading to comparable weld seam strengths over the entire range of tested feed rates. Optimal feed rates can be assumed in the range of $v = 2500 \dots 3500 \text{ mm/min}$ at a laser power of $P_L = 100 \text{ W}$ and in the range of $v = 7000 \dots 9000 \text{ mm/min}$ at a laser power of $P_L = 200 \text{ W}$. At a

laser power of $P_L = 100W$, it was observed that once the feed rate adjusted outside the optimal range, the heat input was not sufficient to generate an adequate joint. Conversely, if the feed rate falls considerably below the optimal range, the heat generation will lead to degradation and porosity in the weld seam (see Figure 8), with a resultant decrease in the recorded strength values.

Figure 8: Exemplary weld seam appearance for an ideal welding parameter set (a) and a parameter set leading to overheating (b).

The samples highlighted in Figure 9 contrast the difference in fracture between that of a good parameter set and that of one that underwent overheating and the associated degradation. It can be seen that the fracture occurred predominantly in the base material for the samples welded with optimal parameters, where the fracture occurred at the welding partners' interface for the samples which overheated.

Figure 9: Exemplary fracture appearance for an ideal welding parameter set (a) and a parameter set leading to overheating (b).

Figure 10: Cross-section micrograph of a TPU specimen welded at ideal parameters.

Cross-section micrographs can be used to visualize and quantitatively evaluate the weld seams. The example shown in Figure 10 highlights the cross-section micrograph produced with ideal welding

parameters, identified by a consistent weld seam height over the entirety of the weld seam width, with no visible porosity or material degradation. Due to the elastic nature of the TPU, the cross-section micrographs cannot be polished as would be convention for other solid materials. As a result, thin film cuts or immersion oil has to be used for this evaluation.

Figure 11: Maximum force obtained for varying specimen treatment at a constant spot size of $A = 10 \times 10 \text{mm}^2$, clamping pressure of $p = 3 \text{bar}$, feed rate $v = 3500 \text{mm/min}$ and laser power $P_L = 100 \text{W}$.

The manufacturer’s material data sheet recommends a tempering treatment of $t = 20 \text{h}$ at a temperature of $T = 100^\circ\text{C}$ to obtain the full mechanical properties after injection molding. Since the welding process inherently causes localized melting, further investigations were carried out to investigate the influence the tempering treatment had on welded samples. Based on the results shown in Figure 11, there is no indication that the tempering treatment had any influence on the tensile strength of laser transmission welded parts.

Investigations were also performed, varying the clamping pressure on the transparent glass plate in the welding setup, revealing a sensitivity to weld seam strength. As can be seen in Figure 12, a decreased weld seam strength was obtained when the clamping pressure was reduced to $p = 1 \text{bar}$. This decline in performance is likely attributed to a reduction in heat transfer at the welding interface which in turn suppressed the mixing of the two welding partners, minimizing the amount of mixed molten material in the weld pool.

Figure 12: Maximum force obtained for varying clamping pressure at a constant spot size of $A = 10 \times 10 \text{mm}^2$, feed rate $v = 3500 \text{mm/min}$ and laser power $P_L = 100 \text{W}$.

Figure 13: Defect simulation; a) artificial gap before welding, b) gap after welding, c) temperature profile during welding, passing an artificial gap.

Through synchronous temperature measurements with high speed pyrometers, it not only allows the temperature in the weld seam to be monitored and controlled to the ideal temperature, but also presents the ability to detect real time temperature changes occurring due to gaps or defects in the welding path. This capability was demonstrated by creating an artificial gap in the weld seam of $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$ filled with a copper wire to simulate a contamination. As shown in Figure 13 a distinct local temperature drop was observed when passing the gap. The temperature drop occurs due to the reduced absorption and the enhanced thermal conductivity of the copper wire. Other defects or contaminating materials would lead to a different temperature profile changes, but once a reference profile is defined, any changes can be detected. This observation can be used as a basis for simultaneous process monitoring in industrial application.

A potential application of the welding process is pictured in Figure 14. In this case a transparent TPU flange was welded onto a c.b. TPU pipe at a laser power of $P_L = 70 \text{ W}$ and a feed rate $v = 3500 \text{ mm/min}$. For this welding process, an adapted rotary stage and clamping system was used to apply pressure outward from inside the tube in efforts to maintain uniform contact between the two parts.

Figure 14: Exemplary application of the welding process.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper a laser transmission welding process for TPU materials was presented, characterized by its wide process parameter range, its robustness and by its process monitoring potential. The TPU material used in the experiments was an Elastollan® 1185A compound. Since laser transmission welding processes require a laser transparent material partner and a laser absorbing partner, natural (laser transparent) TPU coupled with a black masterbatch (laser absorbing) containing compound were selected for use in the experiments. The clamping pressure needed for a proper heat transfer between the two overlapping parts was applied by pneumatic clamping. Tensile testing was performed on the welded samples to characterize the welding strength.

The results revealed a wide processing parameter range for the feed rate wherein sufficient weld seam strengths were achieved. Sufficient weld seam strengths were achieved with feed rates as high as $v = 10000\text{mm/min}$, operating at a laser power of $P_L = 200\text{W}$. Investigations were also performed, varying the clamping pressure, revealing a sensitivity to weld seam strength.

The pyrometer temperature measurement showed good capabilities in terms of a synchronous temperature monitoring in order to sustain ideal welding temperatures as well as for defect monitoring by recording deviations e.g. local temperature drops. This observation can be used as a basis for simultaneous process monitoring in industrial applications. Combined with the wide process parameter range, a robust and highly reliable welding process is provided.

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